

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

Bima Rizky Xanditama¹, Mahrinasari², Roslina³

^{1,2,3} Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Lampung

ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the effect of marketing on customer loyalty at Dunkin' Donuts in Indonesia. Despite its long presence in the Indonesian market and the implementation of sensory marketing strategies through visual, auditory, olfactory, tactile, and gustatory elements, Dunkin' Donuts has experienced a decline in customer loyalty and faces challenges competing with local brands such as J.Co. This research employs a quantitative approach with a survey method using Likert-scale questionnaires, analyzed through multiple regression techniques. The results indicate that all sensory marketing elements significantly influence customer loyalty, with visual and gustatory elements as dominant factors. The study confirms that a strong sensory experience can create emotional attachment and enhance customer loyalty. These findings provide strategic implications for companies in designing more appealing and memorable brand experiences to maintain market share in the highly competitive food and beverage industry.

KEYWORDS: Sensory Marketing, Customer Loyalty, Dunkin' Donuts, Food Industry

INTRODUCTION

The business landscape in Indonesia has experienced continuous growth over the years, driven by the persistent contributions of entrepreneurs and investors across various thriving industrial sectors. From manufacturing and transportation to the food and beverage industry, these sectors are rapidly evolving, reflecting the increasingly competitive dynamics of the market. Within this context, customer loyalty plays a critical role in ensuring the long-term success of a business. Particularly in the food and beverage sector, customer loyalty is of utmost importance as it directly relates to consumers' decisions to continue purchasing and utilizing a brand's products or services. Loyalty not only reflects customer satisfaction but also stems from the emotional bonds formed between consumers and brands. In this dynamic industry—where consumer preferences tend to shift rapidly based on trends and experiential factors—companies must consistently deliver added value to remain relevant in the eyes of their customers (Chinomona & Sandada, 2013).

According to Hulten (2011), sensory marketing involves stimulating all five senses—sight, sound, smell, touch, and taste—to create a profound and memorable brand experience. Through sensory marketing, brands can directly target and influence customers' emotions, which is a foundational element of customer loyalty. Visual stimulation and customer loyalty, according to Hulten (2011) and Krishna (2020), are heavily influenced by visual elements such as packaging design, color, and product layout. These are often the first aspects noticed by consumers during brand interactions. Consistent use of brand-aligned colors and designs can enhance consumer recall and strengthen positive brand associations.

Indonesia's food industry has undergone significant transformation over the past few decades, fueled by the rise of the middle class, urbanization, and shifts in modern consumption patterns. Data from the Ministry of Industry shows that the food and beverage sector contributed more than 36% to the manufacturing Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2023, making it one of the largest economic sectors in the country. Amid intensifying competition, food businesses are expected not only to offer quality products but also to create unique experiences that attract consumer attention. In this regard, strong brand experiences supported by effective sensory marketing have become key factors in achieving differentiation, capturing customer interest, and maintaining market share in this dynamic industry.

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

GDP Data of the Food and Beverage Industry in Indonesia

Figure 1. GDP Data of the Food and Beverage Industry in Indonesia

Source: Statistics Indonesia (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2023)

Figure 1 shows that in Q1 2023, the food and beverage industry's GDP at constant prices (ADHK) reached IDR 206.19 trillion, marking a 5.33% year-on-year growth from IDR 195.75 trillion in the same period of the previous year (BPS, 2023). This growth placed the food and beverage industry as the fourth-largest contributor among processing industry subsectors, following the metal goods, base metals, and transportation equipment industries, which grew by 12.78%, 15.51%, and 17.27% (yoy), respectively.

This development has drawn numerous foreign companies to open outlets in Indonesia, including Krispy Kreme and Mister Donut, as well as local competitors such as J.Co Donuts. J.Co launched its first store in May 2006 after years of research and development. Initially targeting young consumers with significant purchasing power, J.Co's first store was strategically located in a shopping center near Pelita Harapan School, owned by the Lippo Group (J.Co, 2022).

In Indonesia, J.Co is now a formidable competitor to the long-established Dunkin' Donuts. Despite its 38-year presence in the Indonesian market and global dominance, Dunkin' Donuts has struggled to maintain its position as the top-selling donut store in the country. Data from the Top Brand Index illustrates this trend:

Table 1. Top Brand Index

BRAND	TBI
J.Co	52.40%
Dunkin Donuts	35.70%
Krispy Kreme	2.00%

Sumber: Top Brand Award 2023 (Top Brand Award, 2023)

The table shows that J.Co currently dominates the donut market in Indonesia, leading by nearly 17% over Dunkin' Donuts. Interestingly, just three years earlier, in 2020, the competition between the two was neck and neck, with only a 0.1% difference: J.Co at 43.4% and Dunkin' Donuts at 43.3%. By 2021, J.Co surged ahead with a TBI of 50.7% compared to Dunkin' Donuts' 38% (Top Brand Index, 2023).

Despite more than three decades of operation in Indonesia and being a pioneer in the donut industry, Dunkin' Donuts faces major challenges in maintaining its market dominance. Robust sensory marketing and consistent brand experiences have proven insufficient to counter the strong competition posed by newer players like J.Co and Krispy Kreme. As shown by the Top Brand Index, Dunkin' Donuts' market share has declined, while local competitors have significantly widened the performance gap.

Considering the suboptimal implementation of certain sensory marketing elements found in prior studies, this research aims to analyze the influence of sensory marketing on customer loyalty toward Dunkin' Donuts in Indonesia. A survey is deemed necessary to capture customer experiences and feedback regarding taste, touch, visual appeal (of both product and store), smell, sound, and customer-brand interactions—encompassing emotional, cognitive, behavioral, and relational aspects affecting

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

satisfaction. The research focuses specifically on Dunkin' Donuts Indonesia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior is a crucial aspect in understanding how and why individuals make purchasing decisions, especially in the context of marketing and business. According to Kotler & Keller (2016), consumer behavior involves the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations select, buy, use, and dispose of goods, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs and desires. This process is influenced by internal factors such as perception, motivation, attitudes, and past experiences, as well as external factors such as culture, social dynamics, and situational variables. Solomon (2018) emphasizes that consumer behavior is influenced by the psychology and emotions experienced during the purchasing process. Brand experiences designed to deliver pleasure or comfort tend to positively influence consumer perceptions, thereby promoting long-term loyalty. Sensory marketing—which encompasses elements such as sound, smell, and visual stimuli—plays a substantial role in shaping consumer experiences.

B. Marketing

Marketing is a series of activities carried out by an organization to create, communicate, and deliver value to customers while fulfilling their needs and wants. It involves market research, product development, pricing, distribution, and promotion to achieve organizational goals. According to Kotler (2016), marketing is a social process through which individuals and groups obtain what they need and want by creating and exchanging valuable products. Stanton and Walker (2007) define marketing as a series of activities designed to plan, price, promote, and distribute goods and services that satisfy the needs of current and potential customers. Marketing is one of the core business functions aimed at fulfilling consumer needs by offering relevant and valuable products and services. Philip Kotler, a renowned marketing expert, describes marketing as “a social and managerial process by which individuals and groups obtain what they need and want through creating, offering, and exchanging products of value with others” (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Marketing goes beyond product promotion and involves comprehensive strategies including pricing, distribution, market research, and the development of long-term customer relationships.

C. Sensory Marketing

According to Odabayy and Barry (2012), sensory marketing is a form of communication with consumers through the use of the five senses—sight, hearing, smell, touch, and taste. This approach aims to engage consumers' senses and create stimulating experiences. Marketing utilizes stimuli designed to trigger sensory responses, and perception occurs when consumers interpret the sensations they experience. The outcome of this perceptual process can influence consumer satisfaction levels.

The American Marketing Association (AMA, 2020) defines sensory marketing as a strategy intended to influence consumer feelings and behaviors through sensory engagement. Stimuli directed at one or more of the senses—such as light intensity, sound levels, fabric texture, detergent scent, or coffee flavor samples—can affect consumer feelings and actions. The following approaches outline the main sensory elements applied in marketing:

- Visual Approach

This approach involves the use of attractive visual elements such as compelling packaging design, store layout, or product displays that capture attention. Appealing visual stimuli can shape consumers' perceptions of the product and brand and spark interest and purchase desire. The visual marketing approach refers to the use of images, colors, designs, and layout to influence consumer perception and behavior.

- Auditory Approach

This method incorporates engaging auditory elements such as appropriate music selection, pleasant background sounds, or sound effects that create a desired atmosphere. Auditory stimuli can influence consumers' mood, emotions, and perception of products or the shopping environment. The auditory approach in marketing focuses on using sound, music, and jingles to affect emotions, perceptions, and consumer behavior. Sound plays a crucial role in establishing atmosphere and emotional connections with a brand, ultimately increasing consumer engagement.

- Olfactory Approach

The olfactory or scent-based marketing approach, also known as aroma marketing, seeks to utilize the sense of smell to create deep emotional experiences and encourage purchasing behavior. Scents have the unique ability to connect directly with emotions and memories, making them a powerful tool in forming positive brand associations.

- Haptic Approach

The haptic or tactile approach in sensory marketing emphasizes the influence of touch on consumer perception and purchasing decisions. Touch is a critical sense when interacting with products, especially when consumers can feel texture, weight, and material quality—factors that impact their judgment of a product's quality and value.

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

- Gustatory Approach

The gustatory or taste-based approach in sensory marketing highlights the importance of taste in shaping consumers' perceptions of a product or brand, particularly within the food and beverage industry. Taste is one of the most direct sensory drivers of purchasing decisions, especially when food and drink are the main focus of a business.

Conceptual Framework

This study analyzes how sensory marketing influences customer loyalty. The following is the framework for thinking in this study:

Figure 2. Research Framework

Hypothesis

The logical relationship between two or more variables is expressed in the form of a testable proposition. By testing hypotheses and verifying the relationship between variables, it is expected that solutions to problems can be found.

1. The visual aspect of sensory marketing influences customer loyalty
2. The auditory aspect of sensory marketing influences customer loyalty
3. The olfactory aspect of sensory marketing influences customer loyalty
4. The tactile aspect of sensory marketing influences customer loyalty
5. The taste aspect of sensory marketing influences customer loyalty

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

This study employs a causal research design, which aims to identify cause-and-effect relationships between the investigated variables. This approach is relevant because interactions between variables in marketing often result in reciprocal effects. Additionally, a descriptive approach is also used to describe the observed variables. The main focus of this research is to analyze the causal relationships between variables such as performance expectations, effort expectations, social influence, facilitating conditions, trust, and intention to use. The study adopts a quantitative method to measure and statistically analyze data.

Data Collection Method

Primary data collection was conducted through a survey, where questions were directly presented to respondents via the Google Forms platform. Respondents were given a series of questions relevant to the research topic, enabling the researcher to gain insights into their perspectives. Surveys offer several advantages. First, questionnaires are easy to organize and manage. Second, the responses provided by participants are limited to the choices in the questionnaire, making the resulting statistical data more reliable.

Population and Sample

Population

The population in this study comprises individuals in Indonesia who have purchased Dunkin' Donuts products directly from Dunkin' Donuts outlets, to be evaluated in terms of customer loyalty.

Sample

This study uses a purposive sampling design, which is a non-probability sampling method where information is collected from a

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

specific group of individuals based on particular criteria. In other words, data are gathered from a group selected because of their relevance to the research objectives. The sample criteria for this study are as follows:

1. Individuals who have purchased from Dunkin' Donuts outlets more than twice;
2. Aged at least 15 years old.

Operational Definition of Variables

This study includes two variables: the independent variable (X) and the dependent variable (Y). The independent variable (X) refers to sensory marketing, while the dependent variable (Y) is customer loyalty.

Data Analysis Techniques

Validity Test

To assess validity, the factor loading value of each indicator is compared to a minimum threshold—commonly set at 0.5. If the factor loading of an item is greater than 0.5, the item is considered valid, as it effectively represents the intended factor.

Reliability Test

Reliability is measured through a one-shot measurement method, where the results are compared with other statements to evaluate inter-item correlation. A variable is deemed reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is greater than 0.6.

Multiple Regression Analysis

T-Test

The t-test is used to determine whether each independent variable (X) individually has a significant effect on the dependent variable (Y).

F-Test

The F-test assesses whether all independent variables (X) simultaneously or collectively have a significant effect on the dependent variable (Y).

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination (R²) measures the extent to which the model explains the variation in the dependent variable. The R² value ranges from 0 to 1.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis

The characteristics of respondents in this study include individuals who have made purchases directly at Dunkin' Donuts stores in Indonesia more than twice. From the distribution of 200 questionnaires, the respondents' characteristics are categorized by gender, age, education, occupation, income, purchasing experience, purchasing frequency, and domicile.

1. Gender

Table 2. Respondent Characteristics by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	78	39
Female	122	61
Total	200	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

The table shows that 61% of respondents are female and 39% are male. This suggests that women tend to consume food and beverages such as Dunkin' Donuts more frequently and are more active in seeking food trends through media. Snacks and sweet beverages like donuts have become part of lifestyle, especially among women (Oktafikasari & Mahmud, 2017).

2. Age

Table 3 Respondent Characteristics by Age

Age Groups	Frequency	Percentage (%)
15-20	72	36
11-26	45	22,5
27-32	48	24
33-38	26	13

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

39-44	7	3,5
>45	2	1
Total	200	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

Table 3 shows that the majority of respondents are in the age range of 15–32 years with a percentage of 82.5%. This shows that Dunkin Donuts consumers in Indonesia are mostly young to early adult age groups who are active and dynamic. This age group tends to be more responsive to modern food and lifestyle trends, and is more open to product innovation and digital promotions. Previous research also shows that young consumers are highly influenced by brand experience factors and sensory marketing in choosing fast food products (Sari & Putri, 2021).

3. Education

Table 4. Respondent Characteristics by Education Level

Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
High School	71	35
Diploma (D1-D4)	27	13,5
Bachelor's Degree	90	45
Master's Degree	12	6
Total	200	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

Table 4 shows that the majority of respondents have a Bachelor's/S1 educational background of 45%. Meanwhile, respondents with a high school or equivalent education reached 35%, diploma (D1-D4) of 13.5%, and Masters/S2 of 6%. This shows that Dunkin Donuts consumers in Indonesia come from various levels of education, but are dominated by those with a Bachelor's degree. Consumers with higher education usually have different levels of awareness and preferences for product quality and brand experience, so it is important for Dunkin Donuts to adjust marketing strategies that can reach these various education segments (Priyono, 2022).

4. Occupation

Table 5. Respondent Characteristics by Occupation

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Students	75	37,5
Civil Servants	44	22
Private Employees	40	20
Entrepreneurs	24	12
Housewives	16	8
Others	1	0,5
Total	200	100%

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

Table 5 shows that the majority of respondents are students or college students as much as 37.5%. Furthermore, civil servants as much as 22%, private employees 20%, entrepreneurs 12%, housewives 8%, and other categories of 0.5%. This data illustrates that Dunkin Donuts consumers in Indonesia come from various work backgrounds, with the dominance of students and college students who tend to be the main market for snack and snack products. This diversity of jobs shows the importance of a marketing strategy that is able to reach various consumer segments with different needs and preferences (Santoso & Rahmawati, 2023).

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

5. Monthly Income

Table 6. Respondent Characteristics by Monthly Income

Income Range (IDR)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<Rp 1.000.000	66	33
Rp 1.000.000-3.000.000	47	23,5
Rp 3.000.000-5.000.000	58	29
Rp 5.000.000-7.000.000	19	9,5
Rp 7.000.000	10	5
Total	200	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

Table 6 shows that the majority of respondents have a monthly income below IDR 1,000,000 as much as 33% and income between IDR 3,000,000 to IDR 5,000,000 reaching 29%. Meanwhile, respondents with This data shows that Dunkin Donuts consumers in Indonesia come from various economic levels, with the largest concentration in the low to middle income group. This is important for Dunkin Donuts in determining pricing and promotion strategies to remain affordable and attractive to various consumer income segments (Hidayat & Sari, 2021).

6. Purchasing Experience

Table 7 Respondent Characteristics by Purchasing Experience

Duration	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<1 years	42	21
1-2 years	57	28,5
2-3 years	51	25,5
>3 years	51	25,5
Total	200	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

Table 7 shows that the majority of respondents have experience as Dunkin Donuts consumers for 1–2 years at 28.5%. In addition, respondents with 2–3 years and more than 3 years of experience are 25.5% each. This data indicates that most Dunkin Donuts consumers already have quite a long experience in consuming the product, which can have a positive effect on their level of loyalty and perception of the brand. Consumers with this experience tend to be more familiar with the product and feel consistent service quality (Wibowo & Prasetya, 2022).

7. Purchase Frequency

Table 8 Respondent Characteristics by Purchase Frequency

Purchase Frequency	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-3 times/month	51	25
3-5 times/month	78	39
>5 times/month	71	35
Total	200	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

Table 8 shows that the majority of respondents make Dunkin Donuts purchases with a frequency of 3-5 times a month at 39%, followed by respondents who buy more than 5 times at 35%. This shows that Dunkin Donuts consumers make purchases quite often, reflecting a high level of loyalty and interest in the product. This high purchase frequency is an indicator of the success of

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

marketing strategies and product quality in maintaining loyal customers (Nugroho & Lestari, 2020).

8. Domicile

Table 9 Respondent Characteristics by Region

Region	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Western Indonesia	88	44
Central Indonesia	58	29
Eastern Indonesia	54	27
Total	200	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

Table 9 shows that most respondents live in western Indonesia at 44%, followed by respondents from central Indonesia at 29%, and eastern Indonesia at 27%. This data indicates that Dunkin Donuts consumers in Indonesia are more spread out in the western region, which generally includes large cities and centers of economic activity. This can be a basis for consideration in formulating product marketing and distribution strategies, with a primary focus on the western region while continuing to expand reach to the central and eastern regions (Putri & Hidayat, 2021).

Respondent Feedback Results

a. Results of Respondents' Responses to the Visual Aspect Variable (X1)

The visual aspect (X1) is a critical component of Dunkin' Donuts' sensory marketing strategy, aiming to deliver an attractive and memorable experience. Based on the average score of the indicators—such as store design, product layout, packaging, use of color, and promotional visuals—the total mean score is 3.43, which falls into the “fairly high” category. This suggests that consumers have a relatively positive perception of the brand's visual presentation in Indonesia.

Table 10 Results of Visual Aspect Variables

Code	Item	F	Answer Score					Total	Mean
			1	2	3	4	5		
X1.1	I find the Dunkin Donuts store display attractive.	F	0	21	79	69	31	200	3.55
		%	0	10.5	39.5	34.5	15.5	100	
X1.2	I find the Dunkin Donuts store display visually appealing.	F	9	18	62	87	24	200	3.49
		%	4.5	9	31	43.5	12	100	
X1.3	I feel like Dunkin Donuts outlets are Attractive	F	6	10	42	104	38	200	3.79
		%	3	5	21	52	19	100	
X1.4	I think the aesthetics of Dunkin Donuts' product layout are very good.	F	0	19	80	38	29	200	2.87
		%	0	9.5	40	19	14.5	100	
Average Total								3.43	

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

Table 10 shows that from each statement on the visual aspect variable (X1), the total average value (mean) is 3.43. This indicates that consumers' visual perception of Dunkin' Donuts outlets is in a fairly high category. This means that consumers have a fairly positive view of the visual aspect of the appearance of Dunkin' Donuts outlets in Indonesia.

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

b. Results of Respondents' Responses to the Hearing Aspect Variable (X2)

Table 11 Results of Hearing Aspect Variables

Code	Item	F	Answer Score					Total	Mean
			1	2	3	4	5		
X2.1	I find the background music at Dunkin Donuts outlets enjoyable.	F	8	22	59	76	35	200	3.45
		%	4	11	29.5	38	17.5	100	
X2.2	I feel the quality of the music played at Dunkin Donuts is very good.	F	5	5	20	156	14	200	3.85
		%	2.5	2.5	10	78	7	100	
X2.3	I feel like the song selection at Dunkin Donuts creates a positive atmosphere.	F	0	16	64	90	30	200	3.67
		%	0	8	32	45	15	100	
X2.4	I find the volume at Dunkin Donuts to be just right for relaxing.	F	0	20	88	72	20	200	3.46
		%	0	10	44	36	10	100	
Average Total								3.63	

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

Based on Table 11, respondents' responses to the auditory aspect variable at Dunkin' Donuts outlets showed quite positive results, with an average total score of 3.63. The majority of respondents stated that the background music at the outlet was pleasant with a score of 3.54, the quality of the music played was very good (3.85), and the selection of songs was able to create a positive atmosphere (3.67). In addition, the volume of the sound was also considered quite appropriate for relaxing, although it got a slightly lower score of 3.46.

c. Results of Respondents' Responses to the Olfactory Aspect Variable (X3)

Table 12 Results of Olfactory Aspect Variables

Code	Item	F	Answer Score					Total	Mean
			1	2	3	4	5		
X3.1	I find the aroma of food at Dunkin Donuts outlets very tempting.	F	0	17	62	89	32	200	3.68
		%	0	8.5	31	44.5	16	100	
X3.2	I feel the aroma at Dunkin Donuts creates a pleasant atmosphere.	F	7	12	40	115	26	200	3.7
		%	3.5	6	20	57.5	13	100	
X3.3	I feel the aroma at Dunkin Donuts is always fragrant and appetizing.	F	5	24	71	85	15	200	3.4
		%	2.5	12	35.5	42.5	7.5	100	
X3.4	I feel like every visit to Dunkin Donuts is accompanied by a tempting aroma.	F	6	19	85	70	20	200	3.3
		%	3	9.5	42.5	35	10	100	
Average Total								3.5	

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

Table 12 shows that from each statement on the smell aspect variable (X3), the total mean value is 3.50. This indicates that consumer perception of the aroma at Dunkin' Donuts outlets is in the fairly high category.

d. Results of Respondents' Responses to the Tactile Aspect Variable (X4)

Table 13 Results of the Tactile Aspect Variables

Code	Item	F	Answer Score					Total	Mean
			1	2	3	4	5		
X4.1	I feel the texture of the packaging at Dunkin Donuts	F	16	19	90	65	10	200	3.17
	provides a pleasant experience.	%	8	9.5	45	32.5	5	100	
X4.2	I feel comfortable when holding Dunkin Donuts	F	8	10	41	114	27	200	3.71
	products	%	4	5	20.5	57	13.5	100	
X4.3	I find the furniture at Dunkin Donuts very comfortable to	F	0	23	88	69	20	200	3.43
	relax in.	%	0	11.5	44	34.5	10	100	
X4.4	I find the texture of the food at Dunkin Donuts appetizing.	F	10	21	72	87	10	200	3.33
		%	5	10.5	36	43.5	5	100	
Average Total								3.41	

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

Table 13 shows that the average score for the tactile aspect (X4) is 3.41, indicating a fairly good perception. Although not very high, a pleasant tactile experience can enhance brand impression and foster emotional customer loyalty

e. Results of Respondents' Responses to the Taste Aspect Variable (X5)

Table 14 Results of Tasting Aspect Variables

Code	Item	F	Answer Score					Total	Mean
			1	2	3	4	5		
X5.1	I feel the taste quality of Dunkin Donuts products is always satisfactory.	F	5	5	20	156	14	200	3.84
		%	2.5	2.5	10	78	7	100	
X5.2	I feel the taste of the food at Dunkin Donuts is up to my expectations.	F	2	14	64	68	52	200	3.77
		%	1	7	32	34	26	100	
X5.3	I find the food at Dunkin Donuts very	F	15	21	91	63	10	200	3.16

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

	delicious and appetizing.	%	7.5	10.5	45.5	31.5	31.5	100	
X5.4	I find the drinks at Dunkin Donuts to be always delicious and refreshing.	F	0	17	82	66	35	200	3.59
		%	0	8.5	41	33	17.5	100	
Average Total									3.59

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

Table 14 shows the recapitulation results of the taste aspect variable (X5), which is related to respondents' perceptions of the taste of food and drinks offered by Dunkin' Donuts. Based on the results of data processing, the total average value (mean) was 3.59. This shows that in general respondents have a fairly good perception of the taste of Dunkin' Donuts products, although it has not reached the very high category.

a. Respondents' Response Results Regarding Customer Loyalty

Table 15 Customer Loyalty Respondent Results

Code	Item	F	Answer Score					Total	Mean
			1	2	3	4	5		
Y1	I always buy Dunkin Donuts food products every month	F	0	22	84	72	22	200	3.41
		%	0	11	42	36	11	100	
Y2	Apart from buying food products, I also bought other products sold at Dunkin Donuts outlets.	F	6	9	43	117	25	200	3.64
		%	3	4.5	21.5	58.5	12.5	100	
Y3	I recommend dunkin donuts to my friends and family to buy dunkin donuts products	F	0	11	63	93	33	200	3.73
		%	0	5.5	31.5	46.5	16.5	100	
Y4	I would not be interested in buying any other food product other than Dunkin Donuts	F	0	14	89	72	25	200	3.54
		%	0	7	44.5	36	12.5	100	
Average Total								3.58	

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2025

Table 15 shows the results of the indicators that measure customer loyalty to Dunkin' Donuts. Based on the results of data processing, it is known that the total mean value is 3.58, which indicates that customer loyalty to Dunkin' Donuts is in the fairly high category. This means that most customers tend to agree that they have an attachment to Dunkin' Donuts products, both in terms of repeat purchases, recommendations, and preferences for the product compared to competitors. The statement with the highest mean value is in indicator Y3, namely "I recommend Dunkin Donuts to my friends and family to buy Dunkin Donuts products" with a mean value of 3.73. This shows that customers are not only satisfied but also believe in the quality of Dunkin' Donuts products so that they are willing to recommend them to others. This is in line with the concept of customer loyalty which is not only limited to repeat purchases, but also the willingness to recommend the brand. Furthermore, the indicator with the second highest mean value is Y2, namely "In addition to buying food products, I also buy other products sold at Dunkin Donuts outlets" with a mean value of 3.64. This finding shows that Dunkin' Donuts customers tend to explore and purchase additional products offered, indicating loyalty not only to the main product.

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

The indicator with a mean value of 3.54 is in statement Y4, which is "I will not be interested in buying other food products besides Dunkin Donuts". This statement shows that some customers have a high preference for Dunkin' Donuts and show an exclusive attitude towards competitor products, although not as high as the previous indicator. Meanwhile, statement Y1, which is "I always buy Dunkin Donuts food products every month", has the lowest mean value of 3.41. Although still in the fairly high category, this value shows that not all customers consistently buy Dunkin' Donuts products every month. This can be caused by several factors such as the location of the outlet, the frequency of needs, or the presence of other alternatives.

Overall, these findings show that Dunkin' Donuts has a fairly strong level of customer loyalty, especially in terms of word-of-mouth and product preference. This result is in line with the Customer Loyalty theory by Oliver (1999) which states that loyalty is not only indicated by repeat purchases, but also by the customer's affective and cognitive commitment to the brand.

DISCUSSION

Based on the research that has been done previously, it shows that the five hypotheses (H1 to H5) are accepted. This means that each variable of Visual Aspect (X1), Hearing Aspect (X2), Olfactory Aspect (X3), Touch Aspect (X4), and Taste Aspect (X5) has a significant partial influence on the Customer Loyalty variable (Y).

1. The Influence of Visual Aspects on Customer Loyalty

Based on the results of partial testing (t-test) conducted in this study, it was found that the Visual Aspect (X1) has a calculated t value $> t$ table ($5.421 > 1.97$) with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_a is accepted. Thus, it can be concluded that the Visual Aspect partially has a positive and significant effect on Dunkin Donuts Customer Loyalty in Indonesia. This finding shows that the stronger the visual experience felt by customers, both through store design, product layout, and food and beverage packaging, the greater the likelihood of customers to remain loyal to the Dunkin Donuts brand. Consistent and attractive visual influences can create a sense of comfort, satisfaction, and trust, so that customers are encouraged to make repeat purchases and recommend products to others.

These results are in line with research conducted by Mulia & Astuti (2021) which states that visual experience has a positive effect on customer loyalty in the food and beverage industry. Another study by Sasmita & Suki (2015) also supports this finding by stating that visual appeal in a shop plays an important role in forming long-term relationships with customers. Thus, it can be said that the Visual Aspect is one of the important elements in a sensory marketing strategy that can significantly strengthen customer loyalty to Dunkin Donuts amidst the competition in the fastfood industry in Indonesia.

2. The Influence of the Aspect of Country on Customer Loyalty

Based on the results of partial testing (t-test), the results obtained that the Aspect of Hearing (X2) has a calculated t value $> t$ table ($2.801 > 1.97$) with a significance level of $0.006 < 0.05$, so H_a is accepted. This means that, partially, the Aspect of Hearing has a positive and significant effect on Customer Loyalty at Dunkin Donuts in Indonesia. This shows that strategically designed sounds in the store environment such as music that matches the brand identity, non-disturbing volume, or the distinctive sound of a coffee machine can provide a memorable experience for customers. A positive audio atmosphere creates a sense of comfort and increases the likelihood of customers returning and recommending to others.

This finding is reinforced by research conducted by Yalch & Spangenberg (2000) which states that music and sound in a retail environment can influence consumer behavior and strengthen emotional attachment to the brand. Similar research by Herrington & Capella (1996) also found that the right background music can extend visit time and increase customer loyalty. Thus, it can be concluded that the Auditory Aspect is an important part of the sensory marketing strategy that can create a pleasant atmosphere and strengthen customer loyalty towards the Dunkin Donuts brand in Indonesia.

3. The Influence of Olfactory Aspect on Customer Loyalty

Based on the results of the partial test (t-test), it was obtained that the Olfactory Aspect (X3) has a calculated t value $> t$ table ($2.256 > 1.97$) with a significance value of $0.025 < 0.05$, so H_a is accepted. Thus, the Olfactory Aspect has a positive and significant effect on Dunkin Donuts Customer Loyalty in Indonesia. These results indicate that the distinctive aroma that comes from products such as coffee, warm donuts, and freshly baked cakes can create a deep impression for customers. The aroma not only increases appetite, but also forms positive associations with the brand that stick in consumers' memories. This study is supported by the findings of Spangenberg et al. (1996) which states that a pleasant aroma can improve consumers' moods, extend the duration of visits, and increase the likelihood of repeat purchases. Other research by Bone & Ellen (1999) also found that aroma has the power to improve consumer experience and strengthen loyalty to a brand.

4. The Influence of Tactile Aspects on Customer Loyalty

Based on the results of the partial test (t-test), it was obtained that the Tactile Aspect (X4) has a calculated t value $> t$ table

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

(2.650 > 1.97) with a significance value of 0.009 < 0.05, so H_a is accepted. This means that the Tactile Aspect has a positive and significant effect on Dunkin' Donuts Customer Loyalty in Indonesia. This shows that the physical experience felt by customers when touching the product such as the soft texture of the donut, the right coffee temperature, or the ergonomic packaging design can add comfort value and strengthen the emotional bond with the brand. In addition, the comfort of the seat, the cleanliness of the table, and the atmosphere of the room also contribute to the pleasant impression felt by customers when they are in the outlet.

This finding is supported by research by Peck and Childers (2003) which states that the tactile aspect can increase consumer emotional involvement and strengthen the intention to repurchase. In addition, research by Hultén (2011) also confirms that touch is an important element in creating a distinctive brand experience and forming long-term loyalty. Thus, it can be concluded that Dunkin' Donuts is able to utilize the tactile aspect in creating a comprehensive consumer experience, which significantly contributes to their customer loyalty.

5. The Influence of Taste Aspect on Customer Loyalty

Based on the results of partial testing (t-test), it was obtained that the Taste Aspect (X5) has a calculated t value > t table (2.752 > 1.97) with a significance level of 0.006 < 0.05, so H_a is accepted. This means that the Taste Aspect has a positive and significant effect on Dunkin Donuts Customer Loyalty in Indonesia. This finding shows that the taste experience provided by Dunkin' Donuts, both in terms of the softness of the donut texture, the combination of delicious toppings, and coffee and tea drinks that suit their taste, significantly contribute to forming customer satisfaction and loyalty. Consumers who are satisfied with the taste of the product tend to make repeat purchases and even recommend it to others.

This study is supported by Krishna's study (2012) which states that taste is the most crucial sensory element in the food and beverage industry because it can directly influence the perception of product quality. In addition, Spence et al. (2014) also emphasized that a consistent and enjoyable taste experience plays an important role in building long-term relationships between brands and their consumers. Thus, it can be concluded that the Taste Aspect is one of the dominant factors that can create customer loyalty to Dunkin Donuts, so the company needs to continue to maintain and improve the quality of its product taste in order to remain competitive and liked by customers.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion that has been conducted regarding the influence of sensory marketing aspects on Dunkin Donuts customer loyalty in Indonesia, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Visual aspects have a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. The interior appearance of the outlet, product packaging, and presentation of Dunkin' Donuts food and beverages are able to attract consumers' attention and create a pleasant visual experience.
2. The auditory aspect also has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. Appropriate background music and friendly service voices help create a comfortable atmosphere, strengthening the emotional connection between customers and the brand.
3. The olfactory aspect shows a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. The distinctive aroma of fresh coffee and donuts can evoke memories and the desire to repurchase the product.
4. The tactile aspect has a significant effect on customer loyalty. The comfort of the seat, the texture of the food, and other physical interactions provide a tactile experience that supports the emotional attachment of customers.
5. The taste or flavor aspect is proven to be the most dominant in influencing customer loyalty. Delicious, consistent, and consumer-appropriate tastes are the main factors for customers to make repeat purchases at Dunkin Donuts.

Suggestion

Based on the results of the analysis, discussion, and conclusions of this study, there are several suggestions that can improve customer experience and their loyalty in the food and beverage industry, so the suggestions that can be submitted in this study are:

1. Maintain and improve the quality of taste (taste) as the most influential aspect in creating customer loyalty. Dunkin' Donuts needs to maintain the consistency of product taste and continue to innovate according to local consumer trends and preferences.
2. Optimize the visual and olfactory aspects in every element of marketing and service, such as interior design, product packaging, and the distribution of distinctive aromas that are characteristic of the brand.
3. Manage the sound (hearing) and touch (touch) experiences strategically to support a comfortable and pleasant atmosphere

The Influence of Sensory Marketing on Customer Loyalty Among Dunkin' Donuts Customers in Indonesia

for customers while in the store.

4. Conduct regular sensory evaluations, either through customer surveys or product trials, to ensure that the experience provided remains relevant and satisfies customers.
5. For further researchers, it is recommended to add other variables outside of sensory marketing, such as customer satisfaction, brand experience, or emotional relationships, so that the research results are more comprehensive and in- depth.

REFERENCES

- 1) American Marketing Association. (2020). Defenition Sensory Marketing. Retrieved January 20, 2024, from American Marketing Association: www.ama.org/definitions/sensory-marketing
- 2) Badan Pusat Statistik. (2023). Statistik PDB Industri Makanan dan Minuman 2023. Retrieved January 03, 2024, from Badan Pusat Statistik: https://www.bps.go.id/id/publication/2020/05/19/46f4771e28_1557c89c35f732/statistik-PDB- industri-makanan-dan-minuman-2023.html
- 3) Barry, T., & Howard, D. (1990). A Review and Critique of the Hierarchy of Effects in Advertising. *International Journal of Advertising*, 9(2), 121-135.
- 4) Bloch, P., Brunel, F., & Arnold, T. (2003). Individual Differences in the Centrality of Visual Product Aesthetics: Concept and Measurement. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 29(4), 551-565.
- 5) Bone, P., & Jantriana, S. (1992). Olfaction as a cue For Production Quality. *Marketing Letters* 3(3), 289-296.
- 6) Brakus, J., Schmitt, B., & Zarantonello, L. (2009). Brand experience: What is it? How is it measured? Does it affect loyalty? *Journal of Marketing*, 73(3), 52-68.
- 7) Bronner, K., & Hirt, R. (2009). Audio Branding: Brands, Sound and Communication. *Music and Marketing* 1(1), 1-15.
- 8) Bruner, G. (1990). Music, Mood, and Marketing. *Journal of Marketing* 54 (4), 94-104.
- 9) Chebat, J., & Michon, R. (2003). Impact of Ambient Odors on Mall Shoppers Emotion Cognition and Spending. *Journal of Business Research*, 529-539.
- 10) Chinomona, R., & Sandada, M. (2013). Customer satisfaction, brand trust and customer loyalty in the retailing sector of the economy of Zimbabwe. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 437-446.
- 11) Dunkin Indonesia. (2024). Kampanye Pemasaran di Media Sosial Dunkin' Donuts.
- 12) Dunkin Indonesia. (2024). Review Pelanggan di Akun Resmi Facebook. Facebook.
- 13) Gentile, C., Spiller, N., & Noci, G. (2007). How to sustain the customer experience: An overview of experience components that co-create value with the customer. *European Management Journal*, 395-410.
- 14) Hagtvedt, H., & Patrick, V. (2008). Art Infusion: The Influence of Visual Art on the Perception and Evaluation of Consumer Products. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 45(3), 379-389.
- 15) Hulten, B. (2011). Sensory marketing: The multi-sensory brand-experience concept. *European Business Review*, 23(3), 256-273.
- 16) J.Co. (2022). J.Co Our Story. Retrieved January 15, 2024, from J.Co Donut: <https://jcodonuts.com/id/id/our-story>
- 17) Krishna, A. (2020). An integrative review of sensory marketing: Engaging the senses to affect perception, judgment and behavior. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 22(3), 110-125.
- 18) Kumar, V., & Shah, D. (2020). Buku Pegangan Penelitian Ekuitas Pelanggan dalam Pemasaran. Edward.
- 19) Pine, J., & Gilmore, J. (1998). Welcome to the Experience Economy. *Harvard Bussiness Review*, 97-105.
- 20) Schmitt, B. (2009). Experiential Marketing: How to Get Customers to Sense, Feel, Think, Act, Relate to Your Company Brands. *Journal Marketing : Free Press*.
- 21) Spence, C. (2019). Pengalaman Multisensori: Saat Indra Bertemu Teknologi. *Journal Management*.
- 22) Suhud, U. (2021). Peran Musik Dalam Pemasaran Sensorik pada Gerai Ritel di Indonesia. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis*, 123-137.
- 23) Top Brand Award. (2023). Top Brand Index 2023. Retrieved Januari 16, 2024, from Top Brand Award: <https://www.topbrand-award.com/top-brand-index>
- 24) Top Brand Index. (2023). Top Brand Award. Retrieved January 15, 2024, from Top Brand Index 2023: <https://www.topbrand-award.com/top-brand-index>
- 25) Zampini, M., & Spence, C. (2012). The Role of Auditory Cues in Modulating the Perceived Crispness and Stanleness of Potato Chips. *Journal of Sensory Studies*, 347-363.
- 26) Zomato. (2022). Ulasan Pelanggan Dunkin' Donuts di Indonesia. Zomato.